

Cases Series of Snake Bite Presented to the Emergency Medicine Department of Tertiary Care Centre

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Abstract:

Venomous snake bite causes significant morbidity and mortality if treatment, especially antivenom therapy, is delayed. The case series discussed here throws insight not only into the presentation of a venomous snake bite to the emergency but also describes the different clinical courses the patient may undergo and management of complications during their hospitalization. One out of 5 patients presented early within 1 hr of bite and other 4 were delayed presentations to our emergency team. Out of them 3 patients had neurotoxic symptoms and one patient developed coagulopathy. One patient underwent fasciotomies for compartment syndrome. One patient required hemodialysis. Four patients underwent intubation for respiratory compromise, and one expired despite of all efforts.

Keywords: snake bite, compartment syndrome, 20WBCT, fasciotomy, POCUS.

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Introduction

According to the WHO snake bite is a neglected health issue in many tropical and subtropical countries. About 5.4 million snake bites occur each year, resulting in 1.8 to 2.7 million cases of envenoming. There are between 81,410 and 137,880 deaths and around three times as many amputations and other permanent disabilities each year due to snake bite. It kills >100,000 people and maims >400,000 people every year [1].

Envenomation is the frequent manifestation, followed by coagulation abnormalities and neurotoxicity. It is thought that snake bites are quite common in rural areas, but urban centres do receive a decent number of snake bite cases mostly during damp and rainy seasons.

Identifying the victims who require early administration of anti-snake venom is the key to the successful management of snake envenomation. India supposed to have more snakebites than any other country. Despite inadequate hospital-based

reporting, estimates of total annual snakebite mortality ranges from about 1,300 to 50,000 in India. [2] The following work done in the department of emergency medicine at Dr.R.M.L.I.M.S. Lucknow describes the WHO syndromic approach to snake bite and the tough task in the management of snake bite envenomation.

Case-1

This 12 years old female, 7th standard student presented in emergency department with chief complains of swelling and inflammation at the site of bite marks on right foot, serosanguinous discharge from site, vomiting, headache, giddiness, weakness, ptosis, slurring of speech, ophthalmoplegia, drowsiness and respiratory paralysis. 20 WBCT (20 minutes whole blood coagulation test)- was clotted. Patient was intubated in emergency triage area in view of hypoxia and low GCS score (E2V1M3).

10 vials of ASV (anti snake venom) were administered followed by inj. atropine 0.5 mg i.v. (intravenously) and inj. neostigmine 1.5 mg i.v. to the patient. Assessing the patient after 30 min. we found condition was not improving. 10 vials of ASV were repeated and second dose of inj. atropine and inj. neostigmine was given and regimen of inj. neostigmine and inj. atropine started.

After the total dose of 30 vials of ASV patient's condition improved. After 24 hrs patient gained consciousness, started following commands, hypoxia was resolved, ABG became normal and

patient was extubated. After 48 hrs of admission to emergency pain, swelling and inflammation increased around the site of bite mark. On examination pain, pallor, parasthesia, pulselessness, poikilothermia were present.

After suspecting compartment syndrome, compartment pressure was measured by using white side's technique and pressure was 34 mm Hg (normal < 30 mm Hg). Fasciectomy was performed and kept under observation. Patient was discharged after 5 days with instructions regarding follow up and dressing of wound.

Figure 1:

Case-2

A 15 years old boy came to our emergency department after having snake bite on neck (double bite). Symptoms of Ptosis, dysarthria was positive at presentation. Pt was immediately administered 10 unit of ASV. Patients 20WBCT was clotted. Patient's single breath count was less than 10 words per breath. POCUS (point of care ultrasonography) showed diaphragmatic paralysis.

Patient was intubated and put on mechanical ventilation and 10 vials of ASV given after intubation. 2 doses of atropine and neostigmine administered but there was no improvement. Suspecting of a krait bite, calcium gluconate was

started and repeated 6 hourly. After 8 hrs of admission again 10 vials of ASV given to pt. (total ASV given was 30 vials). After 3 days patient gained consciousness, GCS improved, following this patient was extubated and kept under observation. After 3 days of extubation patient was discharged.

Case-3

A 39 years old male came to emergency department with suspected snake bite on left hand. According to relatives it was black coloured snake with strips. Patient was referred to us from district hospital where he was given 15 unit of anti -snake venom. On presentation to us patient had ptosis,

difficulty in swallowing, breathing and decreased breath counts. POCUS (point of care ultrasonography) showed diaphragmatic paralysis. 20 WBCT was clotted. Patient was given 10 unit of ASV (anti-snake venom) within 1 hour. (Total ASV given to pt. - 30 vials in divided doses). In view of poor GCS (E2V1M2) patient was intubated and kept on mechanical ventilation. Despite 2 doses of Atropine and neostigmine there was no improvement further. Calcium gluconate was stated and repeated 6 hourly. Patient had 2 episodes of generalised tonic clonic seizures for which antiepileptics were started. NCCT head was within normal limits. Patient developed fever, agitation with increased secretions and was unable to maintain oxygen saturation (SpO₂). Secretions decreased on adding inj. glycopyrrolate. After 12 hrs of regular suctioning and monitoring patient settled. GCS improved and patient was extubated and kept on non-invasive ventilation. Patient was discharged after 10 days of admission.

Case-4

A 48 years old male was bitten by snake at right foot. Patient reached district hospital after 1 hour of bite. Patient was given 10 vials of anti -snake venom in district hospital and then referred to our tertiary care centre. On arrival in emergency during primary survey patient was in gasping state with low GCS (E1V2M1). Patient was intubated and kept on mechanical ventilation. We performed 20 WBCT immediately which was not -clotted. 10 vials of ASV were administered. After 1 hr again 20WBCT was done which was not clotted. Total 30 vials of ASV were administered to patient in our hospital. During his ventilator stay patient developed sepsis (serum procalcitonin - 30), bleeding from nose and endotracheal tube. PT/INR was raised. Subsequently 8 unit of FFP (fresh frozen plasma) was transfused. NCCT brain showed large infarct in middle cerebral artery territory. Later patient expired after 8 days from admission despite ventilatory support.

Case- 5

A 56 years old male came to emergency department with history of snake bite on his left foot while working in field. Patient complaints were severe pain at the bite site and gum bleeding. 20 WBCT was performed which was not-clotted indicating coagulopathy. 10 vials of ASV were administered. Routine blood investigations sample was sent. After 30 minutes again 20 WBCT was performed which remained not-clotted, following this another 10 vials of ASV was administered. Inj. Vitamin K followed by 4 units of FFP was given. At 6 hours 20 WBCT was performed which was still not-clotted, 10 vials of ASV was administered at this stage and repeated after 6 hours. (Total ASV 40 vials administered to patient). Blood

investigations showed increased creatinine level >5 mg/dl, INR >2. Patient developed oliguria for which hemodialysis was performed. Hemodialysis done on every alternate day till the urine output improved and creatine came to normal levels. INR also came to normal level by this time. Patient's general condition improved and he was discharged after 7 days of admission.

Discussion

The management of a snake bite victim is often challenging. In country like India the presenting features can be complicated by locally available traditional treatment. Patient can present with features of systemic toxicity due to redistribution of venom. Thrombin-like enzymes (TLEs) are serine proteases, found mainly in pit viper venoms that induce coagulopathy. Hypofibrinogenemia is a usual result of fibrinogen degradation by TLEs [3]. Most of the viper-induced coagulopathy is attributed to these thrombin - like enzymes. Cobra and Krait are both mainly neurotoxic. In general Snake venom contains cardiotoxin, neurotoxin, myotoxin, haemotoxin, and nephrotoxin. The effect of these toxins includes local wound necrosis, rhabdomyolysis, acute kidney injury, coagulopathy etc. Neurotoxins can lead to paralysis of extremities, respiratory distress. In south East Asia region where housing infrastructure and resources are not very good especially in rural areas most of snake bites occur at night because majority of people sleep in open or on the floor [4]. There are several cases reported in the available literature highlighting the initial clinical presentations however, case series which include the initial clinical presentation, the hospital course, and management of complications have not been published in the literature. In our series out of five patients presented to us with an alleged history of snake bite 4 were males and 1 was female of paediatric age group. One out of 5 patients presented early within 1 hr of snake bite and other 4 were delayed presentations to our emergency team. Out of them 3 patients had neurotoxic symptoms and one patient developed coagulopathy. One patient underwent fasciotomies for compartment syndrome. One patient required hemodialysis. Four patients underwent intubation for respiratory compromise, and one expired despite of all efforts.

Conclusion

Snake bite victims show varied clinical presentations ranging from local signs to systemic signs of envenomation. The patients who initially seem to be "stable" in emergency, can have an erratic course and can land up in life-threatening complications, even death. Hence, it is of paramount importance for an emergency physician to recognize the signs of envenomation, to

administer anti-snake venom in time if envenomation exists, he must closely monitor clinical and laboratory parameters to recognize if there are any additional doses of anti-snake venom required. It is important to timely secure the airway in cases of respiratory failure and shock. Treating physician must be vigilant to recognize signs of compartment syndrome and a multi-disciplinary team approach is required for managing coagulopathy, cardiac arrhythmias, respiratory failure, acute kidney injury and other possible complications if they arise during management of patient.

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